

Construction and Analysis of Binomial Coefficients

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Abstract: This paper discusses the construction and analysis of the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-9]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-9] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

$V_n^r = V_r^n$ is an important binomial identity of combinatorial geometric series.

3. Construction of Various Binomial Coefficients

$V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$

$N = \{V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ is a set of natural numbers.

$W = \{0, V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ is a set of whole numbers.

$Z = \{\dots, -V_2^1, -V_1^1, -V_0^1, 0, V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, \dots\}$ is a set of integers.

$$V_n^1 = \frac{(n+1)}{1!}; V_n^2 = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!}; V_n^3 = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)}{3!}; \dots; V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+r)}{r!}$$

Here, $V_n^1 = V_1^n; V_n^2 = V_2^n; V_n^3 = V_3^n; V_n^4 = V_4^n; V_n^5 = V_5^n; \dots$

$$V_{n-1}^1 = \frac{n}{1!}; V_{n-1}^2 = \frac{n(n+1)}{2!}; V_{n-1}^3 = \frac{n(n+1)(n+2)}{3!}; \dots; V_{n-1}^r = \frac{n(n+1)\dots(n+r)}{r!}$$

Here, $V_{n-1}^1 = V_1^{n-1}; V_{n-1}^2 = V_2^{n-1}; V_{n-1}^3 = V_3^{n-1}; V_{n-1}^4 = V_4^{n-1}; V_{n-1}^5 = V_5^{n-1}; \dots$

Let q be a real or complex number, i.e. $qV_i^r = \mu_i$, (for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).

Then μ_i is also a real or complex number.

$\{\mu \mid -\infty < \mu < \infty\}$ is a set of real numbers, where ∞ denotes infinite symbol.

$\{\mu_a + i\mu_b \mid -\infty < \alpha < \infty \text{ and } -\infty < \beta < \infty\}$ is a set of complex numbers and μ_a, μ_b are real numbers for all a & $b = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

4. Conclusion

In this article, construction and analysis of the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series were discussed for further research and development. These ideas can enable the researchers to solve the scientific real world problems.

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